

Sorghum Juice from the 'Super 2' Variety: A Promising Carbon Source for Oleaginous Yeast in Biodiesel Production

Mauritz Nicolaas Wattimena¹, Toga Pangihotan Napitupulu², Atit Kanti³,
Idris², Leonard Wijaya⁴, Miftahul Ilmi⁵, Wijanarka Wijanarka¹,
Fatmawati⁶, I Made Sudiana^{2,7,*}

¹Department of Biology, Diponegoro University, Semarang, Indonesia

²Research Center for Applied Microbiology, National Research and Innovation Agency, Bogor, Indonesia

³Research Center for Biosystematics and Evolution, National Research and Innovation Agency, Bogor, Indonesia

⁴Research Center for Environmental and Clean Technology, National Research and Innovation Agency, Bandung, Indonesia

⁵Faculty of Biology, Universitas Gadjah Mada, Yogyakarta, Indonesia

⁶Research Center for Food Crops, National Research and Innovation Agency, Bogor, Indonesia

⁷Faculty of Medicine Malahayati University, Bandar Lampung, Indonesia

*Author to whom correspondence should be addressed:

E-mail: imad003@brin.go.id

(Received April 29, 2024; Revised February 05, 2025; Accepted April 01, 2025)

Abstract: This study investigates cost-effective substrates for yeast-driven biodiesel production, focusing on sweet sorghum 'Super 2' juice. *Lipomyces starkeyi* InaCC Y-285, *Candida orthopsilosis* InaCC Y-302, and *Candida oleophila* InaCC Y-306 were cultured with adjusted carbon concentrations. Glucose 4%+Sorghum Juice medium significantly increased biomass to 8.03, 8.64, and 6.94 g.L⁻¹ and lipid content by 26.60, 33.77, and 48.72% compared to Glucose 12% medium. These strains predominantly produced oleic and stearic acids in this medium, emphasizing Glucose 4%+Sorghum Juice's potential for efficient biodiesel production by oleaginous yeasts.

Keywords: carbon source; fatty acid composition; lipid accumulation; oleaginous yeasts; sorghum

1. Introduction

The global energy crisis, partly fueled by the depletion of fossil fuel reserves¹, underscores the urgency of exploring sustainable energy alternatives, including microbial sources. Microbes, such as cyanobacteria²⁻⁴ and yeast, can produce Single Cell Oil (SCO), which could be considered a biodiesel source⁵.

Biodiesel, known as Fatty Acid Methyl Ester (FAME), is a renewable yet sustainable fuel, making it a promising alternative to conventional diesel⁶⁻⁷. It offers a viable and environmentally friendly substitute for fossil fuel, which its consumption in Indonesia is expected to continue rising overyear⁸⁻¹⁰. In practical, the developed biodiesel could also just be blended with the conventional diesel to reduce the carbon footprint¹¹.

Yeasts, classified as unicellular eukaryotic organisms within the Fungi Kingdom, reproduce through sexual

means, such as spore production, and asexual methods, like budding or fusion¹². It is widely recognized that yeasts have the capacity to synthesize lipids containing long-chain fatty acids akin to those in vegetable oils. These microbial lipids can be selectively converted into biodiesel using inorganic catalysis or enzymatic processes. Traditionally, yeast species were believed to accumulate lipids comprising up to 4% of their cell dry weight (CDW)¹³. However, certain oleaginous yeast strains can amass more than 20% lipids relative to their CDW. Specific yeast strains, such as those belonging to the genera *Cryptococcus*, *Lipomyces*, *Rhodotorula*, *Trichosporon*, and *Yarrowia*, have been observed to accumulate lipids constituting up to 40% of their CDW^{5,14-15}. A study conducted by Kanti et al. revealed that *Candida orthopsilosis* InaCC Y-302 produced 42.78% total lipids in a 4% glucose medium with limited nitrogen, while *Candida oleophila* InaCC Y-302 yielded 42.23%¹⁶. Under

particular cultural conditions, such as nitrogen limitations, these yeasts have shown the capability to store as much as 60-70% of their CDW in lipids¹³). The yeast strain *Lipomyces starkeyi* NBRC 10381 cultured on a YM agar medium could produce fatty acids (FA) at a rate of approximately 70%¹⁷).

A suitable yet economically friendly growth medium is essential for oleaginous yeast to produce lipids efficiently. In yeast cultivation, carbon sources stand out as the primary cost factor¹⁸). Glucose presently serves as the most commonly used c-source for yeast culture media. Whereas, the high prices of glucose could account for more than half of the total production costs¹⁹). Economical lipid production, therefore, necessitates the use of inexpensive substrates²⁰).

Previous studies have showcased the success of lipid-producing by oleaginous yeasts in alternative specific substrates. Cyanobacteria *Leptolyngbya* HS-16 cultured in 240 ppm NPK as an economic media can obtain lipids up to 58%^{4,21}). Research by Kanti and Sudiana highlighted that the yeast strain *C. orthopsilosis* Yo9GS34 could generate lipids constituting up to 63.75% of the biomass by utilizing carboxymethyl cellulose as its substrate²²). Yeast *Candida orthopsilosis* cultivated on cassava waste media produced 25.6% lipids²³). Hence, alternative eco- and cost-friendly substrates such as waste, crops, and others are considered promising support for oleaginous yeasts to accumulate lipids.

Juice extracted from the stems of the *Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench local variety, known as 'Super 2,' was utilized, boasting a brix level of approximately 13.90%²⁴). Agricultural waste like this should be utilized as a useful material, like biofuel, that could decrease the surrounding pollution²⁵). That particular sorghum variant is renowned for its remarkable biomass yield and bioethanol production capabilities, yielding an alcohol content of 8-10% when fermented²⁴). Previous research in Indonesia has primarily focused on utilizing sorghum juice as a substrate for bioethanol production. For instance, Febrianti demonstrated that sorghum sap media could lead to bioethanol concentrations of up to 4.14% by the sixth day²⁶). Similarly, Rodiyah reported ethanol yields of up to 14.05% and 10.73% when yeast was cultivated on sorghum syrup medium supplemented with 0.5% nitrogen content²⁷).

This research aims to determine the most efficient and practical carbon source combination for lipid production based on lipid yield. By utilizing sorghum juice, we promote a low-cost and environmentally friendly carbon source for potential oleaginous yeast strains, ultimately enhancing lipid production for biodiesel applications. This endeavor aligns with the broader goal of advancing to sustainable energy solutions, particularly in response to the ongoing global energy crisis.

2. Materials Methods

2.1. Materials

The juice in this research was gained from the stems of the 'Super 2' sweet sorghum plant, a local variety of *Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench. This sorghum variety was acquired from the Research Center for Cereal, National Research and Innovation Agency (BRIN) Indonesia, and stored in a freezer until needed. The oleaginous yeasts employed in this research were sourced from the Indonesian Culture Collection (InaCC). Strains InaCC Y-302 and InaCC Y-306 were isolated from the *Piper betle* leaves in Mount Salak, West Java¹⁶). Meanwhile, InaCC Y-853 has been isolated from the soil surrounding the *Chinchona ledgeniana* tree in Ciwidey, West Java.

2.2. Yeasts cultivation

The yeast strains were initially cultured on PDA for 72 hours. Subsequently, colonies of yeast were inoculated into YM Broth media comprising dextrose (10 g.L⁻¹), yeast extract (3 g.L⁻¹), malt extract (3 g.L⁻¹), and peptone (1 g.L⁻¹). These cultures were then incubated at 28°C and 180 rpm in a rotary shaker for 24 hours. Then, around 5% of the inoculum was transferred into a 100 mL of modified medium A (MedA+) in a 250 mL Erlenmeyer flask. This medium composition included glucose (120 g.L⁻¹), CaCl₂ (0.1 g.L⁻¹), NH₄Cl (1.5 g.L⁻¹), yeast extract (1.5 g.L⁻¹), KH₂PO₄ (7 g.L⁻¹), Na₂HPO₄·2H₂O (2.5 g.L⁻¹), MgSO₄·7H₂O (1.5 g.L⁻¹), FeCl₃·6H₂O (0.08 g.L⁻¹), ZnSO₄·7H₂O (10 mg.L⁻¹), MnSO₄·4H₂O (0.07 mg.L⁻¹), CuSO₄ (0.01 mg.L⁻¹), and Co(NO₃)₂ (0.063 mg.L⁻¹)^{16, 28}). Media modification involved manipulating the c-source at various concentrations: Glucose 12% (Glu12), Glucose 2%+Sorghum Juice (Glu2+SJ), Glucose 4%+Sorghum Juice (Glu4+SJ), and Sorghum Juice only (SJ), followed by incubation at room temperature for 72 hours. These were repeated three times for each strain. After the incubation period, all cultures were centrifuged to separate the cells. Subsequently, they were washed first, then dried overnight in an oven at 50°C. Their weight was then measured gravimetrically once completely dry.

2.3. Determination of total sugar composition

The compositions of glucose, fructose, and sucrose in sorghum juice were determined through HPLC analysis. Separation using HPLC (Shimadzu, Japan) was performed with acetonitrile:water (84:16) as the mobile phase at a flow rate of 0.8 mL.min⁻¹. The column (Shimadzu Shim-Pack GIST NH₂, 15 cm length, 5 µm particle diameter) and refractive index detector were maintained at 40°C during analysis. Before analysis, standard solutions were prepared and measured.

2.4. Analysis of total sugar value

To determine the total sugar value, the phenol-sulfuric acid

method outlined by Nielsen²⁹⁾ was employed with slight modifications. Initially, 2 mL of the diluted sample was pipetted, followed by adding 50 μ L of 80% phenol, which was then vortexed. Around 1 mL of sulfuric acid, then, was added and vortexed, after which the mixture was cooled for 10 minutes in a 25°C water bath. Finally, the absorbance of the sample solution was measured using a Varioskan LUX microplate reader (ThermoFisher, United States) at a wavelength of 490 nm. The absorbance values were then calculated using glucose solutions of known concentrations as standards.

2.5. Analysis of total lipid content

Bligh and Dyer³⁰⁾ method with modification by Kanti et al.¹⁶⁾ was used to determine the total lipid content. Initially, 40 mg of dry biomass was extracted using a chloroform:methanol (1:2, v.v⁻¹). After homogenization for one minute, the samples were centrifuged at 2057g for 15 minutes at room temperature. The supernatant was then collected and subjected to two additional extractions (1:1, v.v⁻¹). Subsequently, the resulting supernatant was filtered using the Whatman filter paper No. 1 and rinsed with Milli-Q water. The extract was then centrifuged for 5 minutes at 2057g. The lower part of the organic phase was collected and freeze-dried to obtain the lipid. The total lipid content was then determined gravimetrically, following the formula as stated below³¹⁾,

$$\text{Lipid Content (\%)} = \frac{\text{lipid weight (g.L}^{-1}\text{)}}{\text{dried cell weight (g.L}^{-1}\text{)}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

The lipid yield coefficient is calculated using the following formula⁹⁾,

$$\text{Lipid Coefficient} = \frac{\text{lipid weight (g.L}^{-1}\text{)}}{\text{total sugars consumption (g.L}^{-1}\text{)}} \quad (2)$$

2.6. Determination of FAME content

The Gas chromatography-mass spectrophotometry (GC-MS) was used to analyze the FAME composition in yeast strains cultivated in the medium exhibiting the highest biomass and lipid production. The method followed the protocol outlined by Kumon et al.³²⁾ with some modifications. Firstly, around 1 mL of 10% methanolic hydrochloric acid and 0.5 mL of methylene chloride were added to the dried cells. Subsequently, the samples were

dried for 3 hours at 50°C to facilitate methyl esterification. After that, 2 mL of saturated sodium chloride solution and 1 mL of hexane were added to halt the reaction. The resulting methyl ester, suspended in hexane, was then injected into GCMS-QP 2010-Ultra (Shimadzu, Japan), utilizing a programmed temperature ramp of 150–250°C with an increment of 5°C.min⁻¹.

2.7. The SEM observation

A modified method from Yamazaki et al. was used for the scanning electron microscope (SEM) observation¹⁷⁾. Initially, the samples underwent two washes with phosphate buffer through centrifugation. The samples were immersed for 1 h in 500 mL of Zymolyase 100T (1 mg.mL⁻¹) to observe the ascopore. Then, they were fixated with 10% of glutaraldehyde for 30 minutes and 1% of osmium tetroxide for 1 h. The samples underwent critical point drying in a Critical Point Dryer EM CPD300 after following complete dehydration in a graded ethanol series and substitution with isoamyl acetate (IAA). They were subsequently coated with platinum and palladium using a Magnetron Sputter JUC-5000 and finally observed using SEM JSM-6060 (JEOL Ltd., Tokyo, Japan) operated at 5 kV.

2.8. Statistical analysis

Statistical and data processing applications were used for analysis. Analysis of variance was conducted to identify significant differences between strains and media. The least significant difference (LSD) test was then used as post-hoc testing, performing with a 95% confidence level ($p \leq 0.05$).

3. Results and Discussions

3.1. Sugar content of sorghum “Super 2” Juice

The total sugar contained in ‘Super-2’ sweet sorghum juice, determined using the phenolic acid-sulfuric method, yielded a result of 135.99 ± 0.75 g.L⁻¹. This value aligns closely with the findings of Pabendon et al., who reported a sugar content of 13.90%²⁵⁾. However, in media Glu2+SJ and Glu4+SJ, where glucose concentrations were added, the total sugar content increased to 156.27 ± 2.64 and 176.32 ± 1.04 g.L⁻¹, respectively (Table 1).

Table 1: Research design for each culture medium using sorghum “Super 2” juice

Culture media	Carbon source(s)	Total sugar contained (g.L ⁻¹)	Temperature (°C)	pH
Glu12	Glucose 12%	120.00 \pm 0.00 ^a	25	5.6
Glu2+SJ	Glucose 2% + Sorghum Juice	156.27 \pm 2.64 ^c		
Glu4+SJ	Glucose 4% + Sorghum Juice	176.32 \pm 1.04 ^d		
SJ	Sorghum Juice	135.99 \pm 0.75 ^b		

Different lowercase superscript letters indicate a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$, $n=3$).

The sorghum plant has garnered significant research attention as a potential alternative c-source for oleaginous

yeast, particularly in biodiesel production³³⁻³⁹). Sorghum is renowned for its high sugar content²⁵). According to HPLC calculations, the ‘Super-2’ variety of sweet sorghum exhibited reducing sugar values of glucose 5.91 g.L⁻¹ and fructose 4.95 g.L⁻¹, alongside a notably high sucrose content of approximately 96.60 g.L⁻¹. Research by Luo et al. indicated that sorghum syrup contained a sugar value of 94.5 g.L⁻¹, with a breakdown of sucrose 42.38 g.L⁻¹, glucose 23.217 g.L⁻¹, and fructose 28.95 g.L⁻¹ ⁴⁰). Additionally, research conducted by Rodiyah demonstrated that sweet sorghum stem sap boasted a high total sugar content ranging from 110–160 g.L⁻¹, comprising approximately 100–144 g.L⁻¹ of sucrose and

7.5–13.5 g.L⁻¹ of reducing sugar²⁷) (Table 2).

Various metabolic processes, transportation mechanisms, and cellular consumption within the plant influence sugar accumulation in sorghum⁴⁰). Differences in the sorghum juice sugar composition can be attributed to a range of factors, including the variety (genetic source), timing of planting and harvesting, duration of storage, morphological characteristics (such as plant height and leaf count), climatic conditions (temperature, rainfall, sunlight exposure, and radiation), genotype, phenological components (such as internode length and diameter), and physiological maturity of the plant⁴¹⁻⁴⁶).

Table 2: The value of sugar content (g.L⁻¹) in sweet sorghum juice of the “Super 2” variety compared to the references

Variety	Total sugar	Sucrose	Reducing sugar			Reference(s)
			Glucose	Fructose	Total	
Super 2	135	96.60	5.91	4.95	10.86	This study
N/A	110-160	100-144	N/A	N/A	75-135	²⁶⁾
Sugar Drip	94.5 (70-110)	42.38	23.21	28.95	N/A	⁴⁷⁾
6AX1022, Jitian 2, Longshi 1, Rio, Shennong No. 2,	170-230	70-130	1-5.6	0.8-4.8	5-30	^{48,49)}

N/A: Data not available.

3.2. Biomass and lipid production enhancement

An increase in optical density (OD) values often indicates the growth of microbial cells in liquid culture media^{50,51}). A higher OD value is crucial as it is the foundation for lipid production in industrial processes^{17,52}). Increased lipid accumulation by oleaginous yeast is anticipated with higher cell numbers in the medium. After a 72-hour incubation period, the Glu4+SJ medium exhibited the highest OD trend among the three yeast strains compared to other treatments (Figure 1). These OD measurements are

further supported by the determination of dry cell weight for the strains following the 72 hours of incubation (Table 1). Consistently, higher biomass yields were observed in the Glu4+SJ medium compared to the Glu12 medium at all strains after 72 h of incubation. The strains exhibited an increase in biomass of up to 40.14% for *L. starkeyi* InaCC Y-853, 11.77% for *C. orthopsis* InaCC Y-302, and 10.15% for *C. oleophila* InaCC Y-306. Notably, strain InaCC Y-853 grown on SJ medium yielded lower biomass than the other two strains, with approximately only 4.40 ± 0.36 g.L⁻¹.

Fig. 1: Cell growth (OD) for 72 h of incubation in various media with different carbon sources, error bars indicate SD, n = 3.

Figure 1A *L. starkeyi* InaCC Y-853, Figure 1B *C. orthopsilosis* InaCC Y-302, and Figure 1C *C. oleophila* InaCC Y-306

The sugar concentration, including glucose, in culture media as feeding substrate is a crucial factor influencing yeast biomass production. Glucose, fructose, and other hexose sugars are transported into yeast cells through facilitated diffusion across the plasma membrane. However, sucrose is required to break down into glucose and fructose by the action of invertase before being transported into the cell. In *Yarrowia lipolytica*, the YHT1 and YHT4 genes are pivotal in this process as they encode the primary hexose sugar transporters responsible for importing sugars into yeast cells⁵³⁻⁵⁵. Once inside the cell, glucose and fructose are rapidly phosphorylated by hexokinase⁵⁶. These sugars undergo oxidative metabolic pathways within yeast cells, ultimately generating maximal energy (ATP) and contributing to biomass formation⁵⁷.

Yeast growth occurs when the microbe utilizes the culture media's sugar as its primary energy source during incubation—the reduction in the total sugar content of the media over time evidences this⁵⁸. In the Glu4+SJ medium, yeast strains InaCC Y-853, Y-302, and Y-306 exhibited the highest total sugar consumption compared to other sorghum juice mediums, reaching 168.22 ± 1.04 g.L⁻¹ ($95.41 \pm 0.56\%$), 155.82 ± 1.10 g.L⁻¹ ($88.41 \pm 0.87\%$), and 150.61 ± 2.62 g.L⁻¹ ($85.47 \pm 2.33\%$), respectively (Figure 2). Variations in total sugar consumption can stem from several factors, including differences in yeast strains even within the same species, as well as variances in the yeast's ability to metabolize its constituent sugar components.

Oleaginous yeasts, in principle, possess the capability to utilize various substrates, including hexose sugars like glucose and fructose⁵⁹. However, glucose is typically utilized more rapidly and is preferred over fructose. As a result, glucose is depleted earlier than fructose during fermentation, leading to variations in sugar consumption^{53,60}. This phenomenon may explain why, in the Glu12 medium, the percentage of total sugar consumption can be maximized, reaching up to $99.24 \pm 0.00\%$ by Y-853, $99.15 \pm 0.06\%$ by Y-302, and $98.13 \pm 0.02\%$ by Y-306. Hexose transporters and hexokinase enzymes play crucial roles in this process, particularly in consuming glucose as the preferred sugar⁵³. While glucose as a substrate in *Y. lipolytica* can be utilized by glucokinase and hexokinase, only hexokinase possesses the capability to utilize fructose⁵⁴.

The type and concentration of c-source present in culture medium crucially influence the growth and lipid titer accumulated by yeast cells⁶¹. Lazar et al. conducted a study demonstrating that genetic modifications to the lipid metabolism system and the overexpression of hexokinase in *Yarrowia lipolytica* resulted in a remarkable 40% increase in FA accumulation from fructose in CDW⁵⁴. Additionally, research by Wang et al. revealed that the yeast strain *Cutaneotrichosporon dermatis*, when cultured on a medium with mixed sugars, glucose and xylose as its carbon sources, exhibited a total lipid content of up to $48.05 \pm 3.51\%$ ⁶². The total lipid content produced by the strains exhibited varying results across each medium, with the highest values consistently observed in the Glu4+SJ medium (Figure 2). In the Glu4+SJ medium, the yeast strain *L. starkeyi* InaCC Y-853 produced lipids at a rate of 4.33 ± 0.289 g.L⁻¹ (Table 3), with a total lipid content around $54.52 \pm 5.48\%$ of its cell biomass and a lipid coefficient of 0.026. Similarly, the yeast strain *C. orthopsilosis* InaCC Y-302 yielded lipids up to 5.18 ± 0.31 g.L⁻¹, achieving a total lipid content of $60.02 \pm 2.04\%$ of its cell biomass in the same medium, with a lipid coefficient of 0.033. Meanwhile, in the Glu4+SJ medium, the yeast strain *C. oleophila* InaCC Y-306 produced lipids reaching 4.09 ± 0.15 g.L⁻¹, with a total lipid content of up to $58.86 \pm 1.02\%$ of its cell biomass and a lipid coefficient around 0.027. These findings indicate that the Glu4+SJ medium enhanced lipid accumulation in yeast by up to 26.60%, 33.77%, and 48.72% compared to the Glu12 medium.

The most significant lipid accumulation in oleaginous yeast occurs at the beginning of the stationary phase²⁸. The 72-hour incubation time, which is still considered within the stationary phase (Figure 1), shows promising biomass and lipid results. Nevertheless, since the Glu4%+SJ treatment already reached the early stationary phase at the 24-hour mark, it is possible that lipid production could be optimized at this time without the need to wait for additional time. This would have a beneficial impact on time, cost, and energy efficiency.

Table 3: Biomass and lipid yield results after 72 h of incubation in various media with different compositions of carbon sources

Yeast Strain	Carbon Source	Cell dry weight (g.L ⁻¹)	Biomass coefficient ²	Lipid (g.L ⁻¹)	Lipid coefficient ³
<i>L. starkeyi</i> InaCC Y-853	Glu12	5.73 ± 0.85	0.052	3.42 ± 0.29	0.029
	Glu2+SJ	6.63 ± 2.48	0.066	2.33 ± 0.14	0.023
	Glu4+SJ	$8.03 \pm 1.27^*$	0.046	$4.33 \pm 0.29^*$	0.026
	SJ	4.40 ± 0.36	0.047	1.58 ± 0.14	0.017
<i>C. orthopsilosis</i> InaCC Y-302	Glu12	$7.73 \pm 0.81^*$	0.065	3.76 ± 0.56	0.032
	Glu2+SJ	$6.91 \pm 0.18^*$	0.050	3.72 ± 0.05	0.027
	Glu4+SJ	$8.64 \pm 0.76^*$	0.055	$5.18 \pm 0.31^*$	0.033

	SJ	6.27 ± 0.15	0.053	3.25 ± 0.25	0.027
C. oleophila InaCC Y-306	Glu12	6.30 ± 0.72	0.054	2.75 ± 0.25	0.023
	Glu2+SJ	6.28 ± 0.35	0.047	2.62 ± 0.11	0.019
	Glu4+SJ	6.94 ± 0.14*	0.046	4.09 ± 0.15*	0.027
	SJ	5.67 ± 0.25	0.048	2.58 ± 0.64	0.022

¹Superscripts indicate a significantly difference ($p < 0.05$, $n=3$). ²Biomass coefficient was counted by dividing the cell dry weight with the total sugar consumption. ³Lipid coefficient was counted by dividing the lipid with the total sugar consumption.

Fig. 2: Total lipid content (% w/w, g lipids per g biomass) and total sugar consumption (% v/v initial sugar) after 72 h of incubation time in various media with different carbon sources, error bars indicate SD, $n = 3$. (A) *L. starkeyi* InaCC Y-853, (B) *C. orthopsilosis* InaCC Y-302, and (C) *C. oleophila* InaCC Y-306. (Glu12 – Glucose 12%, Glu2+SJ – Glucose 2% + Sorghum Juice, Glu4+SJ – Glucose 4% - Sorghum Juice, SJ – Sorghum Juice)

Compared to similar studies, the total lipid content produced by the two yeast strains on the Glu4+SJ medium demonstrated higher results. For instance, Matsakas et al. reported that the yeast strain *L. starkeyi* CBS 1807 could accumulate lipids by 29.5% in sweet sorghum juice media³⁸. Moreover, still with the same medium, the yeast strain *Rhodotorula toruloides* CCT 0783 was found to accumulate lipids of only 33.1% with a lipid coefficient of up to 0.105³⁷. In another study by Rolz et al., yeast cultured in a sorghum juice medium exhibited relatively low lipid accumulation after seven days of incubation. Strain *Yarrowia lipolytica* CBS 2075 accumulated lipids of only 16.18%, followed by *Trichosporon oleaginosus* DSMZ 11815 at approximately 15.89%, *L. starkeyi* CBS 1807 at 14.07%, and *Rhodotorula glutinis* var *glutinis* CBS322 at 13.29%³⁹. It is worth noting that reducing the available nitrogen during the growth stage can enhance carbon utilization for lipid storage⁵³. When nitrogen levels decrease in yeast cells, an enhancement of citric acid excretion happens, increasing acetyl-CoA accumulation, which triggers the FA synthesis. This increase is linked to the citric acid cycle suppression resulting from a decrease in Adenosine Monophosphate (AMP) levels, which

inhibits the isocitrate dehydrogenase enzyme from converting isocitrate to α -ketoglutarate⁶³.

3.3. Fatty Acid Composition

A crucial step in utilizing yeast-produced triacylglycerols (TAGs) as biodiesel involves methyl esterification, where TAGs are converted into FAMES. This process, known as transesterification, entails the reaction of TAG molecules composed of three long-chain FAs bonded to a glycerol molecule with three molecules of alcohol, typically methanol or ethanol. This reaction results in the production of three molecules of methyl ester or ethyl ester biodiesel and one molecule of glycerol⁶⁴. These reaction products are then analyzed using GC-MS to examine the different compounds generated during the reaction⁶⁵. The results revealed the FAME composition produced by each strain. Strain *L. starkeyi* InaCC Y-853 demonstrated the synthesis of 30.81% oleic acid (18:1) around and 42.11% linoleic acid (C18:2). Similarly, *C. orthopsilosis* InaCC Y-302 exhibited the ability to produce 33.53% stearic acid (C18:0) and 66.47% oleic acid. The FAME composition identified in *C. oleophila* InaCC Y-306 included 4.56% myristic acid (C14:0), 15.46% stearic acid, 47.26% oleic

acid, 20.27% linoleic acid, 10.23% linolenic acid (C18:3). The FA composition of oleaginous yeast can vary, depending on the specific strain or species used and the culture environment's conditions⁶⁶. Oleic acid often appears as the dominant FA in these yeasts due to the presence of $\Delta 9$ desaturase. This enzyme converts stearic acid, a saturated FA, into oleic acid, a monounsaturated fatty acid (MUFA), by introducing a double bond at the $\Delta 9$ position^{33,67}. In this study, it is noteworthy that linoleic acid was the predominant FA produced by *L. starkeyi*, which suggests the involvement of gene expression mediated by elongase and desaturase enzymes. Yeast *L. starkeyi* possesses genes like LsFAD2 and LsFAD3, which encode FA desaturases. LsFAD2 encodes $\Delta 12$ FA desaturase, responsible for converting oleic acid into linoleic acid, while LsFAD3 encodes $\Delta 12/\Delta 15$ bifunctional FA desaturase, which can convert oleic acid into both linoleic acid and linolenic acid⁶⁷. Previous research by Matsuzawa et al. indicated that alterations in these genes' expression levels could lead to the accumulation of linoleic acid⁶⁸. Interestingly, this study found palmitic acid (C16:0) and palmitoleic acid (C16:1) undetectable, which could be attributed to the involvement of genes like LsElo2 that encode FA elongase. Overexpression of LsElo2 has been associated with a decrease in C16 FAs (palmitic acid and palmitoleic acid), yet an increase in C18 FAs (oleic acid and linoleic acid)⁶⁹. Upon analysis of the yeast strains cultivated on a Glu4+SJ medium using GC-MS, it was observed that the final compositions produced by these strains exhibited variation.

The resulting structure of the TAGs synthesized was influenced by the random substitution of acyl-CoA groups to glycerol. However, findings from previous studies on oleaginous microorganisms have consistently shown that unsaturated FAs tend to occupy the sn-2 position of glycerol in most cases⁷⁰. Therefore, it was anticipated that the dominant FA in strains InaCC Y-302 and InaCC Y-306 would be oleic acid, a MUFA. This result is supported by a study conducted by Antonopoulou et al. on the *Trichosporon fermentans* yeast strain CBS 439.83, cultured in sweet sorghum stem juice, which revealed that oleic acid was the highest-produced FA, accounting for 37.9% of the total composition⁷¹.

Recent research indicates that oleic acid stands out as the most advantageous lipid for producing high-quality biodiesel⁷²). This FA possesses exceptional chemical and physical properties, including elevated calorific value, cetane index, pour point, cloudiness, density, and kinematic viscosity⁷³). Notably, a substantial amount of oleic acid was produced in a study involving *C. orthopsilosis* InaCC Y-302 and *C. oleophila* InaCC Y-306 cultured in the Glu4+SJ medium. This medium holds considerable promise in enhancing biodiesel yield using oleaginous yeast. Microscopic observation revealed that these two yeast strains exhibited a bright green color when viewed with contrast lighting under a microscope (Figure 3). This observation suggests that the yeast can accumulate lipids in its cytoplasm, which this characteristic that has been documented in previous studies^{74,75}).

Fig. 3: Yeast cells cultured in Glu4+SJ medium under the microscope, bar = 10 μ m, *C. orthopsilosis* InaCC Y-302 with (A) LM (x1000) and (B) SEM (x10000), *C. oleophila* InaCC Y-306 with (C) LM (x1000), and (D) SEM (x10000)

The optimal strategy for lipid production using three distinct oleaginous yeast strains entails employing a blend of 4% glucose and sorghum juice. This particular combination enhances yeast biomass and total lipid content more efficiently than a medium solely composed of glucose. Additionally, these yeast strains yield oleic and stearic acids, which can serve as crucial feedstock for biodiesel production. Further refinement of this medium could involve exploring a broader range of oleaginous yeast strains or experimenting with alternative types of sorghum juice.

Optimizing the incubation time can also be an important and interesting consideration for the continuation of this research. As is well known, numerous factors can influence the lipid content produced by oleaginous yeast, including the species and strain of yeast used, growth stage, carbon-to-nitrogen ratio (C/N) along with their respective concentrations, acclimatization, aeration level, temperature, presence of alcohol, phosphorus concentration, vitamins (such as thiamine and biotin), and pH⁵). These factors can all be considered as parameters to optimize biomass growth and lipid production during the initial incubation period. Thus, reducing and improving production cost efficiency could become feasible, especially for upscaling and future industrial application.

Acknowledgments

We acknowledge the funding of Joint Collaboration Research Program—Research Organization of Life Science and Environment BRIN (No.1/III.5/HK/2024), and Joint Collaboration Research Program—Research Organization of Energy and Manufacture BRIN,- Exploration and Expedition LPDP program No B-1116/II.7.5/FR.06/3/2024-B-949/III.5/FR.06.00/3/2024, Research Grant of Research Organization of Life Sciences and Environment No. 3/III.5/HK/2025. All authors acknowledge the support and funding provided by the BRIN, Indonesia. We extend our heartfelt appreciation to the Energy and Manufacturing Research Organization (BRIN) and the Biodiversity and Environmental Research Organization (BRIN) for their invaluable support in providing the necessary chemicals and research facilities. We also want to thank Ismu Purnaningsih for her invaluable assistance in analyzing FAME and sugar content using GC-MS and HPLC. A special thanks also goes to Yeni Yuliani for providing the yeast cultures essential for this research.

References

- 1) M.C. Duruyurek, C. Dugun, M.F. Gulhan, and Z. Selamoglu, "Production of Bioethanol from Waste Potato," *Turk. J. Agric*, 3 331–334 (2015) doi:10.24925/turjaf.v3i5.331-334.277.
- 2) A. Rahman, N.B. Prihantini, and Nasruddin, "Biomass Production and Synthesis of Biodiesel from Microalgae *Synechococcus* HS-9 (Cyanobacteria Cultivated Using Bubble Column Photobioreactors)," *Evergreen*, 7(4) 564 – 570 (2020). doi:10.5109/4150507.
- 3) A.M. Orlando, Nasruddin, Sjamsuridzal, W., Wardhana, W., and Prihantini, N. B, "Biomass Production and Lipid Content of *Leptolyngbya* HS-16 grown in Bubble Column Photobioreactors (BCPBR) with Air Bubbler Pore Variation," *Evergreen*, 8(4) 885–889 (2021). doi: 10.5109/4742137.
- 4) N.B. Prihantini, N. Rakhmayanti, S. Handayani, W. Sjamsuridzal, W. Wardhana, and Nasruddin, "Biomass Production of Indonesian Indigenous *Leptolyngbya* Strain on NPK Fertilizer Medium and its Potential as Source of Biofuel," *Evergreen*, 7(4) 593-601 (2020). doi:10.5109/4150512.
- 5) I.R. Sitepu, L.A. Garay, R. Sestric, D. Levin, D.E. Block, and J.B. German, "Oleaginous yeasts for biodiesel: Current and future trends in biology and production," *Biotechnol. Adv*, 32 1336–1360 (2014). doi:10.1016/j.biotechadv.2014.08.003.
- 6) J.A. Hidayat, B. Sugiarto, "Characteristic, Structure, and Morphology of Carbon Deposit From Biodiesel Blend," *Evergreen*, 7(4) 609–614 (2020). doi:10.5109/4150514.
- 7) I. Paryanto, T. Prakoso, B. H. Susanto, and M. Gozan, "The Effect of Outdoor Temperature Conditions and Monoglyceride Content on the Precipitate Formation of Biodiesel-Petrodiesel Blended Fuel (BXX)," *Evergreen*, 6(1) 59–64 (2019). doi:10.5109/231010.
- 8) A. Soemanto, E. Mohi, M. I. al Irsyad, and Y. Gunawan, "The Role of Oil Fuels on the Energy Transition toward Net Zero Emissions in Indonesia: A Policy Review," *Evergreen*, 10(4) 2074–2083 (2023). doi:10.5109/7160867.
- 9) A. Kuncoro, and W. W. Purwanto, "Analysis of Energy-Water Nexus Palm Oil Biodiesel Production in Riau Using Life Cycle Assessment and Water Footprint Methods," *Evergreen*, 7(1) 104–110 (2020). doi:10.5109/2740965.
- 10) E. A. Saputro, W. Saputro, and B. W. Saputro, "An Investigation of Engine Performance and Exhaust Gas Emissions under Load Variations using Biodiesel Fuel from Waste Cooking Oil and B30 Blend," *Evergreen*, 10(4) 2255–2264 (2023). doi:10.5109/7160901.
- 11) S. Chaudhary, P. Kumar, and S. Dangi, "Performance Study of Mustard Oil Bio-diesel Blend in a Single Cylinder 4-stroke Diesel Engine," *Evergreen*, 10(1) 317 – 323 (2023). doi:10.5109/67810866.
- 12) S. Phale, "Yeast: Characteristics and economic significance," *J. Bioprocess Biotech*, 8(5) 2155-9821 (2018). doi:10.4172/2155-9821.1000337.

- 13) K.D. Anjani, and M. Ilmi, "Penapisan Isolat Khamir Oleaginous dari Nektar Bunga dan Madu Hutan," *Jurnal Mikologi Indonesia*, 2 99–111 (2018). doi:10.46638/jmi.v2i2.42.
- 14) J.M. Ageitos, J.A. Vallejo, P. Veiga-Crespo, and T.G. Villa, "Oily yeasts as oleaginous cell factories," *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.*, 90 1219–1227 (2011). doi:10.1007/s00253-011-3200-z.
- 15) Q. Wang, B. Cui, W. Ma, R.L. Zheng, X. Liu, and Q. Wang, "Characterization and robust nature of newly isolated oleaginous marine yeast *Rhodospiridium* spp. from coastal water of Northern China," *ABM Express* 7 30 (2017). doi:10.1186/s13568-017-0329-x.
- 16) A. Kanti, E. Sukara, K. Latifah, N. Sukarno, and K. Boundy-Mills, Indonesian oleaginous yeasts isolated from Piper betle and *P. nigrum*, *Mycosphere*, 4 1015–1026 (2013). doi:10.5943/mycosphere/4/5/15.
- 17) A. Yamazaki, A. Kanti, and H. Kawasaki, "Three novel lipomycetaceous yeasts, *Lipomyces maratuensis* sp. nov., *Lipomyces tropicalis* sp. nov., and *Lipomyces kalimantanensis* f.a., sp nov. isolated from soil from the Maratua and Kalimantan Islands, Indonesia," *Mycoscience* 58 413–423 (2017). doi:10.1016/j.myc.2017.06.002.
- 18) O. Gorte, M. Kugel, and K. Ochsenreither, "Optimization of carbon source efficiency for lipid production with the oleaginous yeast *Saitozyma podzolica* DSM 27192 applying automated continuous feeding," *Biotechnol. Biofuels*, 13 (2020). doi:10.1186/s13068-020-01824-7.
- 19) B. Vasconcelos, J.C. Teixeira, G. Dragone, and J.A. Teixeira, "Oleaginous yeasts for sustainable lipid production—from biodiesel to surf boards, a wide range of "green" applications," *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.*, 103 3651–3667 (2019). doi:10.1007/s00253-019-09742-x.
- 20) R. Poontawee, W. Lorliam, P. Polburee, and S. Limtong, "Oleaginous yeasts: Biodiversity and cultivation," *Fungal Biol.* 44 100295 (2023). doi:10.1016/j.fbr.2022.11.003.
- 21) S.R. Ardiansyah, A.M. Orlando, A. Rahman, N. B. Prihantini, and Nasruddin, "Tubular Photobioreactor: A preliminary Experiment Using *Synechococcus* sp. (Cyanobacteria) Cultivated in NPK Media for Biomass Production as Biofuel Feedstock," *Evergreen*, 6(2) 157–161 (2019). doi:10.5109/23210111.
- 22) A. Kanti, and I.M. Sudiana, "Carboxymethyl cellulose as a C-source for lipid accumulation by the oleaginous yeast *Candida orthopsilosis*," *Curr. Res. Environ.*, 5 349–356 (2015). doi:10.5943/CREAM/5/4/4.
- 23) A. Kanti, and I.M. Sudiana, "Co-culture of Amylolytic Fungi *Aspergillus niger* and Oleaginous Yeast *Candida orthopsilosis*," *Berita Biologi*, 16 111–119 (2017). doi:10.14203/beritabiologi.v16i2.2207.
- 24) M.B. Pabendon, R. Efendi, S.B. Santoso, B. Prastowo, Varietas of sweet sorghum Super-1 and Super-2 and its equipment for bioethanol in Indonesia," *IOP Conf. Ser.: Earth Environ. Sci.*, 65(012054) (2017). doi:10.1088/1755-1315/65/1/012054.
- 25) J. Waluyo, M.M. Setianto, N. R. Safitri, S.H. Pranolo, A.D. Susanti, Margono, Paryanto, "Characterization of Biochar Briquettes from Coconut Shell with the Effect of Binder: Molasses, Cow Manure and Horse Manure," *Evergreen*, 10(1) 539–545 (2023). doi:10.5109/6782158.
- 26) S. Febrianti, "Penapisan Khamir untuk Produksi Bioetanol dari Nira Sorghum bicolor L," IPB University, 2017. <https://repository.ipb.ac.id/handle/123456789/83603>.
- 27) S. Rodiyah, "Optimasi Produksi Bioetanol dari Sirup Sorgum (*Sorghum Bicolor*) Menggunakan Khamir Potensial dari Batang dan Biji Sorgum," Brawijaya University, 2018. <https://repository.ub.ac.id/id/eprint/168637/1/SITI%20RODIYAH.pdf>.
- 28) I.R. Sitepu, R. Sestric, L. Ignatia, D. Levin, J.B. German, and L.A. Gillies, "Manipulation of culture conditions alters lipid content and fatty acid profiles of a wide variety of known and new oleaginous yeast species," *Bioresour. Technol.* 144 (2013). doi:10.1016/j.biortech.2013.06.047.
- 29) S.S. Nielsen, "Total Carbohydrate by Phenol-Sulfuric Acid Method," Springer, 2017. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-44127-6_14.
- 30) E.G. Bligh, and W.J. Dyer, "A rapid method of total lipid extraction and purification," *Can. J. Biochem* 37 911–917 (1959). doi:10.1139/o59-099.
- 31) M. E. Osman, A. B. Abdel-Razik, K. I. Zaki, N. Mamdouh, and H. El-Sayed, "Isolation, molecular identification of lipid producing *Rhodotorula diobovata*: optimization of lipid accumulation for biodiesel production." *J. Genet. Eng. Biotechnol.* 20 (2022). doi:10.1186/s43141-022-00304-9.
- 32) Y. Kumon, T. Yokochi, T. Nakahara, M. Yamaoka, and K. Mito, "Production of long-chain polyunsaturated fatty acids by monoxenic growth of labyrinthulids on oil-dispersed agar medium," *Cells*, 60 275–280 (2002). doi:10.1007/s00253-002-1086-5.
- 33) J.E. Lee, P.V. Vadlani, and D. Min, "Sustainable Production of Microbial Lipids from Lignocellulosic Biomass using Oleaginous Yeast Cultures," *J. Sustain. Bioenergy Syst.* 7 36–50 (2017) doi:10.4236/jsbs.2017.71004.
- 34) Y. Liang, K. Jarosz, A.T. Wardlow, J. Zhang, and Y. Cui, "Lipid Production by *Cryptococcus curvatus* on

- Hydrolysates Derived from Corn Fiber and Sweet Sorghum Bagasse Following Dilute Acid Pretreatment, *Appl. Biochem. Biotechnol.*, 173 (2014). doi:10.1007/s12010-014-1007-y.
- 35) Y. Liang, T. Tang, T. Siddaramu, R. Choudhary, and A.L. Umagiliya, "Lipid production from sweet sorghum bagasse through yeast fermentation," *Renew. Energ.*, 40 130–136 (2012). doi:10.1016/j.renene.2011.09.035.
 - 36) Y. Liang, T. Tang, A.L. Umagiliya, T. Siddaramu, M. McCarroll, and R. Choudhary, "Utilization of sorghum bagasse hydrolysates for producing microbial lipids," *Appl. Energy*, 91 451–458 (2012) doi:10.1016/j.apenergy.2011.10.013.
 - 37) L. Matsakas, N. Bonturi, E.A. Miranda, U. Rova, and P. Christakopoulos, "High concentrations of dried sorghum stalks as a biomass feedstock for single cell oil production by *Rhodospiridium toruloides*," *Biotechnol. Biofuel*, 8 (2015). doi:10.1186/s13068-014-0190-y.
 - 38) L. Matsakas, A.A. Steriorti, U. Rova, and P. Christakopoulos, "Use of dried sweet sorghum for the efficient production of lipids by the yeast *Lipomyces starkeyi* CBS 1807," *Ind. Crops Prod.*, 62 367–372 (2014). doi:10.1016/j.indcrop.2014.09.011.
 - 39) C. Rolz, R. León, and A.L. Montenegro, "Co-production of ethanol and biodiesel from sweet sorghum juice in two consecutive fermentation steps," *Electron. J. Biotechnol.*, 41 13–21 (2019). doi:10.1016/j.ejbt.2019.05.002.
 - 40) R.K. Lestari, "Response of biomass, grain production, and sugar content of four sorghum plant varieties (*Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench) to different plant densities," *Open Agric. J.*, 6 761–770 (2021). doi:10.1515/opag-2021-0055.
 - 41) J.H. Bernal, "Effects of the genotype and environment interaction on sugar accumulation in sweet sorghum varieties (*Sorghum bicolor* [L.] Moench) grown in the lowland tropics of Colombia," *Agron. Colomb.* 32 (2014). doi:10.15446/agron.colomb.v32n3.45477.
 - 42) I. López-Sandin, G. Gutiérrez-Soto, A. Gutiérrez-Díez, N. Medina-Herrera, and E. Gutiérrez-Castorena, "Biomass and sugar production dynamics in sweet sorghum variety Roger," *Chil. J. Agric. Res.*, 81 92–101 (2021). doi:10.4067/S0718-58392021000100092.
 - 43) S.R. Morey, Y. Hashida, R. Ohsugi, J. Yamagishi, and N. Aoki, "Evaluation of performance of sorghum varieties grown in Tokyo for sugar accumulation and its correlation with vacuolar invertase genes *SbInv1* and *SbInv2*," *Plant. Prod. Sci.*, 21 328–338 (2018). doi:10.1080/1343943X.2018.1510737.
 - 44) A. Nur, S.B. Santoso, K. Syahrudin, R. Efendy, E.G. Lestari, Study of interaction between genetic source, harvest time and storage time in some mutant varieties of sweet sorghum to support future bioindustry development, *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* 250 (2019) 012068.
 - 45) M.O. Oyier, J.O. Owuochi, M.E. Oyoo, B. Mulianga, and J. Rono, "Effect of Harvesting Stage on Sweet Sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* L.) Genotypes in Western Kenya," *Sci. World J* 8249532 (2017). doi:10.1155/2017/8249532.
 - 46) H.T. Thao, T.V. Dien, and T.D. Xuan, "Effects of Sowing Time on the Growth Development and Productivity of Sweet Sorghum," *J. Sustain. Bioenergy Syst* 5 61395 (2015). doi:10.4236/jsbs.2015.54012.
 - 47) Z. Luo, L.A. Wang, Shahbazi, "Optimization of ethanol production from sweet sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor*) juice using response surface methodology," *Biomass Bioenergy*, 67 53–59 (2014). doi:10.1016/j.biombioe.2014.04.003.
 - 48) H.V. Amorim, L.C. Basso, and M.L. Lopes, "Sugar cane juice and molasses, beet molasses, and sweet sorghum: Composition and usage, The Alcohol Textbook," Nottingham University Press, 2009. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Henrique-Amorim-4/publication/281296915_Sugar_cane_juice_and_molasses_beet_molasses_and_sweet_sorghum_Composition_and_usage/links/58b95571a6fdcc2d14d9b2aa/Sugar-cane-juice-and-molasses-beet-molasses-and-sweet-sorghum-Composition-and-usage.pdf.
 - 49) FAO, "Ethanol production from sweet sorghum," FAO, 1994. <https://www.fao.org/3/t4470e/t4470e07.htm#4.1.%20components%20of%20sweet%20sorghum%20stem%20juice>.
 - 50) J.A. Myers, B.S. Curtis, and W.R. Curtis, "Improving accuracy of cell and chromophore concentration measurements using optical density," *BMC biophysics*, 6(1) 1-16 (2013). doi: 10.1186/2046-1682-6-4.
 - 51) E.A. Rozana, S.H. Anwar, and M.I. Sulaiman, "Potensi Minyak Mikroalga dan Khamir Sebagai Sumber Asam Lemak Esensial." *Jurnal Teknologi Industri Pertanian*, 332-342 (2021) doi:10.24961/j.tek.ind.pert.2021.31.3.332.
 - 52) I. Gientka, M. Wirkowska-Wojdyła, E. Ostrowska-Ligeża, M. Janowicz, L. Reczek, A. Synowiec, and S. Błażejczak, "Enhancing Red Yeast Biomass Yield and Lipid Biosynthesis by Using Waste Nitrogen Source by Glucose Fed-Batch at Low Temperature," *Microorganisms*, 10(6), (2022). doi:10.3390/microorganisms10061253.
 - 53) P. Hapeta, P. Szczepańska, T. Witkowski, J.M. Nicaud, A.M.C.-L. Coq, and Z. Lazar, "The Role of Hexokinase and Hexose Transporters in Preferential

- Use of Glucose over Fructose and Downstream Metabolic Pathways in the Yeast *Yarrowia lipolytica*,” *Int. J. Mol. Sci.*, 22 9282 (2021). doi:10.3390/ijms22179282.
- 54) Z. Lazar, C. Neuvéglise, T. Rossignol, H. Devillers, N. Morin, and M. Robak, “Characterization of hexose transporters in *Yarrowia lipolytica* reveals new groups of sugar porters involved in yeast growth,” *Fungal Genet. Biol.*, 100 1–12 (2017). doi:10.1016/j.fgb.2017.01.001.
- 55) Z. Lazar, T. Rossignol, J. Verbeke, A.M.C.-L. Coq, J.M. Nicaud, and M. Robak, “Optimized invertase expression and secretion cassette for improving *Yarrowia lipolytica* growth on sucrose for industrial applications,” *J. Ind. Microbiol. Biotechnol.*, 40 1273–1283 (2013). doi:10.1007/s10295-013-1323-1.
- 56) L. Mocke, “Kinetic Modelling of Wine Fermentations: Why Does Yeast Prefer Glucose to Fructose?” University of Stellenbosch, 2013. <https://scholar.sun.ac.za/items/785a4890-2500-4a9f-85e7-e779f9165b17>.
- 57) E.D. Vieira, “Yeast biomass production: a new approach in glucose-limited feeding strategy,” *Braz. J. Microbiol.*, 44 551–558 (2013). doi:10.1590/S1517-83822013000200035.
- 58) E. Kusdiyantini, and A. Budiharjo, “The Antioxidant Growth and Potency of Yeast *Rhodospiridium paludigenum* DUCC Y-007 on Different Mediums,” *Jurnal Sains dan Matematika*, 22 97–101 (2014).
- 59) Y.H.V. Soong, N. Liu, S. Soon, C. Lawton, and D. Xie, “Cellular and metabolic engineering of oleaginous yeast *Yarrowia lipolytica* for bioconversion of hydrophobic substrates into high-value products,” *Eng. Life Sci.*, 19 423–443 (2018). doi:10.1002/elsc.201800147.
- 60) J. Tronchoni, A. Gamero, F.N. Arroyo-López, E. Barrio, and A. Quero, “Differences in the glucose and fructose consumption profiles in diverse *Saccharomyces* wine species and their hybrids during grape juice fermentation,” *Int. J. Food Microbiol.*, 134 237–243 (2009). doi:10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2009.07.004
- 61) A. Thanapimmetha, N. Peawsuphon, Y. Chisti, M. Saisriyoot, and P. Srinophakun, “Lipid production by the yeast *Lipomyces starkeyi* grown on sugars and oil palm empty fruit bunch hydrolysate,” *Biomass Convers. Biorefin.*, 11 1197–1210 (2021). doi:10.1007/s13399-019-00532-z.
- 62) L. Wang, D. Wang, Z. Zhang, S. Cheng, B. Liu, and C. Wang, “Comparative Glucose and Xylose Countilization Efficiencies of Soil-Isolated Yeast Strains Identity *Cutaneotrichosporon dermatis* as a Potential Producer of Lipid,” *ACS Omega*, 5 23596–23603 (2020). doi:10.1021/acsomega.0c02089.
- 63) F. Spier, J.G. Buffon, and C.A. Burkert, “Bioconversion of Raw Glycerol Generated from the Synthesis of Biodiesel by Different Oleaginous Yeasts: Lipid Content and Fatty Acid Profile of Biomass,” *Indian J. Microbiol.*, 55 415–422 (2015). doi:10.1007/s12088-015-0533-9.
- 64) D.Y. Leung, X. Wu, and M. Leung, “A review on biodiesel production using catalyzed transesterification,” *Appl. Energy*, 87 1083–1095 (2010). doi:10.1016/j.apenergy.2009.10.006.
- 65) S. Nabilla, S.F. Annisa, K. Zara, and S. Bismo, “Fatty Acid Methyl Ester Synthesis in the Cold Plasma Reactor using CO₂ and Steam Mixture,” *Evergreen*, 7(2) 275–279 (2020). doi:10.5109/4055232.
- 66) M.N. Mota, P. Mugica, and I. Sa-Correia, “Exploring Yeast Diversity to Produce Lipid-Based Biofuels from Agro-Forestry and Industrial Organic Residues,” *J. Fungi*, 8 (2022). doi:10.3390/jof8070687.
- 67) H. Takaku, T. Matsuzawa, K. Yaoi, and H. Yamazaki, “Lipid metabolism of the oleaginous yeast *Lipomyces starkeyi*,” *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.*, 104 6141–6148 (2020). doi:10.1007/s00253-020-10695-9.
- 68) T. Matsuzawa, T. Maehara, Y. Kamisaka, S. Ara, H. Takaku, and K. Yaoi, “Identification and characterization of $\Delta 12$ and $\Delta 12/\Delta 15$ bifunctional fatty acid desaturases in the oleaginous yeast *Lipomyces starkeyi*,” *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.*, 102 8817–8826 (2018). doi:10.1007/s00253-018-9345-2.
- 69) T. Matsuzawa, Y. Kamisaka, T. Maehara, H. Takaku, and K. Yaoi, “Identification and characterization of two fatty acid elongases in *Lipomyces starkeyi*,” *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.*, 104 2537–2544 (2020). doi:10.1007/s00253-020-10401-9.
- 70) S. Papanikolaou, and G. Angelis, “Lipids of oleaginous yeasts. Part I: Biochemistry of single cell oil production,” *Eur. J. Lipid Sci. Technol.*, 113 1031–1051 (2011). doi:10.1002/ejlt.201100014.
- 71) I. Antonopoulou, A. Spanopoulos, and L. Matsakas, “Single cell oil and ethanol production by the oleaginous yeast *Trichosporon fermentans* utilizing dried sweet sorghum stalks,” *Renew. Energ.*, 146 1609–1617 (2020). doi:10.1016/j.renene.2019.07.107.
- 72) Y. Chen, X. Nie, J. Ye, Y. Wang, J. Chen, and J. Xu, “Biodiesel from Microorganisms: A Review,” *Energy Technol.* 9 (2021). doi:10.1002/ente.202001053.
- 73) P. Moradi, M. Saidi, and A.T. Najafabadi, “Biodiesel production via esterification of oleic acid as a representative of free fatty acid using electrolysis technique as a novel approach: Non-catalytic and catalytic conversion,” *Process Saf. Environ. Prot.*, 147 684–692 (2021). doi:10.1016/j.psep.2020.12.032.

- 74) M. Radulovic, O. Knittelfelder, A. Cristobal-Sarramian, D. Kolb, H. Wolinski, and S.D. Kohlwein, "The emergence of lipid droplets in yeast: current status and experimental approaches," *Current genetics*, 59 231-242 (2013). doi:10.1007/s00294-013-0407-9.
- 75) K. Ravikumar, J. Dakshayini, and S. Girisha, "Biodiesel production from oleaginous fungi," *Int J Life Sci Biotechnol Pharma Res.*, 6(1) 43-49 (2012). doi:10.3126/ijls.v6i1.5721.cvxg.